

Kinetics of oxidation of alcohols : phase transfer catalysis

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The study involves the phase transfer catalyzed oxidation of alcohols, namely, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, *n*-heptanol and *n*-hexanol, and kinetics of the oxidation of the alcohols by quaternary ammonium permanganate (tricaprylylmethylammoniumpermanganate). The oxidation of each alcohol by permanganate ion is found to be first order with respect to each of the reactants resulting in an overall second order rate expression.

Phase transfer catalyzed reactions have attracted many researchers for conducting useful synthetic reactions. Gibson and Hosking¹ were the first to report on phase transfer catalytic oxidation. They oxidized water-insoluble reactants in organic media by pairing the permanganate ion with a quat, a lipophilic cation. Sam and Simons² found that dicyclohexyl-18-crown-6 could solubilize solid potassium permanganate in benzene solution, which was used to oxidize a number of organic substrates resulting in good yields of the products. Herriott and Picker³ extracted the permanganate ion from aqueous solution into benzene using different quaternary ammonium salts. Menger *et al.*⁴ carried out two-phase permanganate oxidation of piperonal to piperonylic acid and reported a 65% yield when cetyltrimethylammoniumbromide was used as PTC. Rao and Rao⁵ carried out the oxidation reactions of benzaldehydes, nitro, chloromethyl substituted benzaldehydes and benzylicyanide by potassium permanganate using different phase transfer catalysts. The oxidation of pentafluoropentanal to the corresponding carboxylic acid with an yield of 77% using sodium permanganate in the presence of tetra ethylammoniumhydrogensulfate was reported by Mahmood *et al.*⁶. Tang *et al.*⁷ prepared 2-ethylhexanoic acid by oxidizing 2-ethylhexanol in the presence of PTC in basic aqueous solution. Oxidation using hydrogen peroxide and aqueous hypochlorite under PTC conditions have also been reported⁸.

The present paper reports the potassium permanganate oxidation of 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, *n*-heptanol and *n*-hexanol using tricaprylylmethylammoniumchloride (Aliquat 336) as phase transfer catalyst and their kinetics were investigated in homogenous situation.

Results and Discussion

The rate equation for the oxidation of alcohols by quaternary ammonium permanganate is expressed as

$$-\frac{dC_Q}{dt} = k_2 C_Q^a C_A^b \quad (1)$$

where, C_Q is $QMnO_4$ (quaternary ammonium permanganate) concentration (g mol/l), C_A the concentration of alcohol (g mol/l) and k_2 the second order rate constant (l/g mol min). The initial concentration of alcohol, C_{AO} was very large and was of the order of 200 to 300 times to that of the concentration of $QMnO_4$. C_A can be essentially considered constant at its initial concentration value of C_{AO} during the course of the reaction. Hence, in eqn. (1), the product $k_2 C_A^b$ can be considered as constant and equal to k_1 . Assuming that the reaction is first order ($a = 1$) with respect of $QMnO_4$, the equation when integrated results in

$$\ln \frac{C_{Q_0}}{C_Q} = k_1 t \quad (2)$$

The experimental data for each of the alcohol was observed to follow a straight-line as per eqn. (2). This indicates that the oxidation of alcohol is a first order reaction with respect to $QMnO_4$ concentration. The assumption that the order of reaction a equal to one is correct. The values of k_1 , that is the slopes of the lines, were determined by the least-square technique (Tables 1 and 2) for various experimental conditions.

The value of b which is the order of reaction with respect to alcohol, was determined as follows. Since $k_1 = k_2 C_{AO}^b$, which on rearrangement gives

$$\log k_1 = \log k_2 + b \log C_{AO} \quad (3)$$

The slope of the log-log plot of k_1 vs C_{AO} will give the value of b . The data were observed to follow this relation with slopes varying from 1.01 to 1.05, indicating that the relation is also first order with respect to alcohol concentration so that the overall order of oxidation reaction of each

Table 1. Reaction rate constants for oxidation of alcohols with various initial concentrations of QMnO₄

2-Ethyl-1-hexanol			<i>n</i> -Heptanol			<i>n</i> -Hexanol		
$C_{QO} \times 10^4$ gmol/l	k_1 min ⁻¹	k_2 l/gmol min	$C_{QO} \times 10^4$ gmol/l	k_1 min ⁻¹	k_2 l/gmol min	$C_{QO} \times 10^4$ gmol/l	k_1 min ⁻¹	k_2 l/gmol min
2.72	0.0212	0.0848	2.29	0.0127	0.127	2.86	0.0358	0.143
3.29	0.0214	0.0856	3.31	0.0119	0.119	3.56	0.0369	0.148
4.53	0.0215	0.0860	4.28	0.0123	0.123	4.56	0.0347	0.139
5.60	0.0215	0.0860	5.61	0.0122	0.122	5.58	0.0349	0.143
$C_{AO} = 0.25$ gmol/l, temp. = 29°			$C_{AO} = 0.1$ gmol/l, temp. = 29°			$C_{AO} = 0.25$ gmol/l, temp. = 28°		

Table 2. Reaction rate constants for oxidation of alcohols with various initial concentrations of alcohol

2-Ethyl-1-hexanol				<i>n</i> -Heptanol				<i>n</i> -Hexanol			
C_{AO} gmol/l	k_1 min ⁻¹	k_2 l/gmol min	k_2 from slope	C_{AO} gmol/l	k_1 min ⁻¹	k_2 l/gmol min	k_2 from slope	C_{AO} gmol/l	k_1 min ⁻¹	k_2 l/gmol min	k_2 from slope
0.20	0.0169	0.0845		0.10	0.0123	0.123		0.20	0.0281	0.141	
0.25	0.0215	0.0860		0.15	0.0180	0.120		0.25	0.0347	0.139	
0.30	0.0255	0.0850	0.086	0.20	0.0239	0.120	0.129	0.30	0.0420	0.140	0.151
0.35	0.0298	0.0851		0.25	0.0351	0.125		0.35	0.0508	0.145	
				0.30	0.0378	0.125					
C_{QO} around 4.54×10^{-4} gmol/l, temp. = 29°				C_{QO} around 4.28×10^{-4} gmol/l, temp. = 29°				C_{QO} around 4.53×10^{-4} gmol/l, temp. = 28°			

Table 3. Reaction rate constants for oxidation at various temperatures

2-Ethyl-1-hexanol			<i>n</i> -Heptanol			<i>n</i> -Hexanol		
Temp. °C	k_1 min ⁻¹	k_2 l/gmol min	Temp. °C	k_1 min ⁻¹	k_2 l/gmol min	Temp. °C	k_1 min ⁻¹	k_2 l/gmol min
17	0.0065	0.0325	21	0.0130	0.065	21	0.0163	0.0815
28	0.0144	0.0721	28	0.221	0.111	28	0.0282	0.1410
41	0.0406	0.2030	41	0.0582	0.291	42	0.0758	0.3790
$C_{QO} = 3.5 \times 10^{-4}$ gmol/l, $C_{AO} = 0.2$ gmol/l			$C_{QO} = 3.67 \times 10^{-4}$ gmol/l, $C_{AO} = 0.2$ gmol/l			$C_{QO} = 3.7 \times 10^{-4}$ gmol/l, $C_{AO} = 0.2$ gmol/l		

of the alcohol is two. The values of k_2 in l/(g mol min) were calculated by dividing k_1 by C_{AO} (Tables 1 and 2) along with k_1 values. The values of k_1 and k_2 for the runs made at different temperatures T , were found to follow the Arrhenius relation, $k = k_0 e^{-E/RT}$ (Table 3). The values of frequency factor k_0 and the activation energy E for each of the alcohol oxidation were then calculated (Table 4).

Table 4. Frequency factor and activation energy

Alcohol	E kcal	$k_0 \times 10^{-8}$ l/(gmol min)
2-Ethyl-1-hexanol	13.92	8.359
<i>n</i> -Heptanol	13.85	11.050
<i>n</i> -Hexanol	13.53	8.100

For all the categories of the experiments conducted, the accuracy and the reproducibility of the data were considered. The maximum uncertainty in the values of measurement of concentrations by UV-spectrophotometer was of the order of 0.1%. The reproducibility of the rate constant was good in all the experimental runs. The correlation coefficient was always above 0.996 at 95% confidence level.

The average values of k_2 for the oxidation of 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, *n*-heptanol and *n*-hexanol (Table 1) was found to

be 0.0856, 0.123 and 0.143 l/(g mol min) for various initial concentrations of QMnO₄, respectively. For different initial concentrations of alcohols, k_2 for 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, *n*-heptanol and *n*-hexanol oxidation were found to be 0.0852, 0.123 and 0.141 l/(g mol min), respectively. However, all the runs were pooled for a particular alcohol at a particular temperature and the average values were determined. For 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, *n*-heptanol and *n*-hexanol oxidation, these average values were found to be 0.0854, 0.123 and 0.142 l/(g mol min), respectively. These values agree within $\pm 5\%$ with the values of k_2 obtained from the slope of the plot k_1 vs $\log C_{AO}$ (Table 2).

The activation energy E and the frequency factor k_0 (Table 4) for each of the oxidation reaction of the alcohols are in the order of 13.53 to 13.92 kcal and 8.1 to 11.05 $\times 10^8$ l/(g mol min). According to Perrin¹⁰ bimolecular reactions are slow if the frequency factors are far less than 10^{11} l/(mol s). The frequency factors obtained in the present investigation are of the order of 1.35 to 1.84 $\times 10^7$ l/(mol s), which indicates that the oxidation reaction of the alcohols by permanganate ion are slow.

Experimental

All chemicals of standard quality were used. All liquids

were freshly distilled. Phase transfer catalyst used was tricapyrylmethylammonium chloride (Aliquat 336). This quaternary ammonium salt on reaction with potassium permanganate in aqueous solution gives the quaternary ammonium permanganate in benzene solution.

Quaternary ammonium permanganate in benzene is easily measured by the absorbance method in uv spectrophotometer (Schimadzu 160). The permanganate ion in benzene solution when paired with quaternary ammonium ions has the maximum absorption wavelength at 525 nm which enabled the direct measurement of the concentration of permanganate ions in benzene solutions. The apparatus consisted of borosilicate glass reactor provided with a stirrer. The reactor was operated in batch. For each homogenous kinetic run, the quaternary ammonium permanganate solution was freshly prepared in benzene solution (purple benzene). According to Herriott and Picker³ quaternary ammonium permanganate in benzene showed 17% disintegration on storage for more than 45 h. However, it was found in the present study that QMnO₄ did not disintegrate on storage for a period of 4 h. For most of the experiments in the present study, the reaction time was <1 h. For every experimental run, the purple benzene was prepared in required concentration by taking a small amount of phase transfer catalyst, Aliquat 336 in benzene. This organic solution was contacted with aqueous potassium permanganate solution. The quaternary ammonium permanganate was formed as shown in eqn. (4) and is referred to as purple benzene. The purple benzene thus formed was separated and was diluted further by adding benzene till the required concentration of QMnO₄ was obtained in the solution. A solution of particular alcohol of known concentration in benzene was prepared separately. This solution in requisite quantity was mixed with a known quantity of purple benzene of known concentration in the batch reactor which was kept in a constant temperature bath. The reaction was followed by measuring the fall in

the absorbance of QMnO₄ from which the concentration (gram mol per litre) was calculated. At various time intervals, samples were taken to measure the absorbance. The oxidation reaction of alcohols by QMnO₄ can be represented as follows⁹ :

In all the runs, the concentration of the respective alcohol was maintained at a very large value compared to the concentration of QMnO₄ so that the change in the alcohol concentration was negligible and the reaction occurred under pseudo-order conditions with respect to QMnO₄. The conditions at which these homogenous kinetic runs conducted were as follows. The initial concentration of QMnO₄ was varied from 2.72 to 5.62×10^{-4} gmol/l. The alcohol concentration was varied from 0.1 to 0.35 gmol/l which was very high compared to QMnO₄ concentration. All the experiments were carried out at the room temperature (29°). However, to study the temperature effects on the reaction, few runs were also made in the range 17–42°. The alcohols studied were 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, *n*-heptanol and *n*-hexanol. The reaction time for all the runs were mostly 20 min.

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